

IMPROVEMENT OF INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN CARBON FIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH CARBON NANOTUBE/POLYSULFONE (CNT/PSF) INTERLEAFS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber/epoxy (CF/EP) composites have been widely used as structural materials in many aerospace applications owing to their superior specific strength and specific elastic modulus. However, interlaminar delamination, the most common failure mode of these composite materials, often occurs due to the inherent brittleness of the epoxy matrix. In this study, a vacuum filtration method was used to fabricate carbon nanotube/polysulfone (CNT/PSF) paper as an interleaf to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness of CF/EP composite laminates. During the curing of epoxy resin, the PSF nanofibers were phase separated from the continuous epoxy matrix to form microspheres while the CNTs were dispersed homogeneously around the PSF. The combined effects of the PSF microspheres and CNTs on delamination toughness were investigated. Double-cantilever-beam (DCB) results showed that interleaving the laminates with CNT/PSF paper increased the mode I interlaminar toughness by 53%. DMA tests confirmed that better compatibility between PSF and epoxy could be achieved by adding CNTs. Also, the CNT/PSF interleaved laminates displayed slight increase in storage modulus near the epoxy glass transition temperature due to the reinforcing effect of CNTs.

1 INTRODUCTION

With high specific strength and elastic modulus, carbon fibre/epoxy (CF/EP) composites have been widely used as structural materials for aerospace applications^[1,2]. However, the inherent brittleness of the epoxy matrix has limited their wider applications and interlaminar delamination is the predominant failure mode of these high performance composite laminates^[3,4]. Many strategies have been developed to overcome this problem, and one of the most popular methods is interleaving, whereby a discrete interlayer (either thermoset or thermoplastic) is inserted between the plies. The interleaves facilitate the formations of mechanical linkages between crack interfaces and tortuous crack paths, increasing mode I and mode II delamination fracture toughness, respectively, of composite laminates^[5]. Many kinds of interleaves exist which include particles^[6], films^[7,8], and nanofibrous membranes^[9] used in CF/EP composites. Electrospun nanofiber mat is a good candidate owing to its unique properties, such as high specific surface area and large porosity, which facilitate easy diffusion of epoxy resin in processing the interleaved composite laminates.

Electrospun nanofibrous mats as interleaves to toughen composite laminates were patented first by Dzenis et al.^[10] In their work, non-woven electrospun fabrics of polybenzimidazole (PBI) were used and mode I fracture toughness was increased by ~15%. Subsequently, many kinds of nanofibrous membranes were used for interlaminar toughening of composite laminates, e.g., nanofibers based on polyamide^[9,11], polyacrylonitrile (PAN)^[12,13], polycarbonate (PC)^[14], polyetherketone cardo (PEK-C)^[15], and polycaprolactone (PCL)^[16].

Although nanofiber-based interleaves can increase the fracture toughness, the lack of compatibility and strong interaction between nanofibers and epoxy introduces processing difficulties. Hence, those polymer nanofibers compatible with epoxy resin, like polysulfone (PSF),^[17,18] have been used to increase the toughness of CF/EP composites. Generally, PSF is dissolved first in epoxy and then phase separated into microspheres during curing of epoxy. In delamination, the crack spreads in a zig-zag fashion as it approaches and leaves the PSF microspheres^[19,20], dissipating higher fracture energy. However, toughening by PSF interleaves also brings loss of in-plane properties.

To improve the toughness and retain the in-plane properties of composite laminates, Li et al.^[21] fabricated CNT/PSF nanofibers as interleaves since CNTs have superior mechanical properties such as high elastic modulus and tensile strength.^[22-25] In their work, PSF solution containing a certain amount of CNTs was prepared for electrospinning, and the hybrid nanofiber mat obtained was then used as interleaves in CF/EP composite laminates. Mode II fracture toughness was found to increase moderately when the CNTs in PSF was 10 wt.%. Although CNTs could be incorporated into PSF nanofibers, the preparation of a uniform CNTs/PSF solution, especially at high CNT loading, was quite difficult; and at relatively high CNT loadings, the solution viscosity could be dramatically increased and electrospinning much harder. Also, even at low loadings, CNTs tend to aggregate within the polymer matrix due to their high van der Waals forces and their long and entangled structure. Consequently, CNT agglomerates rather than individual nanotubes occur in the nanofibers, which can limit the increase in or even deteriorate the mechanical performance of CF/EP laminates.

Another issue for CNT/PSF nano-fibers as interleaves is that most CNTs are enveloped inside the PSF microspheres after phase separation from the epoxy. In this case, CNTs cannot play a direct role to enhance the toughness of the composite laminates. Thus, it is desirable that CNTs can be homogeneously dispersed in epoxy matrix rather than in PSF microspheres; their high aspect ratio then yields a large interfacial interaction area with epoxy and they act as nano-bridges in the crack-wake, increasing the toughness.^[26] Besides, when the crack propagates along the interlaminar region, CNTs in the crack paths will cause crack deflection or pull-out from the epoxy matrix.^[5,27]

In this work, CNTs were uniformly deposited on both sides of the electrospun PSF nano-fibrous membranes, forming a sandwich composite, which was used as interleaves in the CF/EP laminates. After curing, PSF was phase separated from the continuous epoxy resin to form microspheres, while CNTs were homogeneously dispersed around the PSF regions. Results of DCB tests demonstrate that the combination of CNTs and thermoplastic PSF as interlayer contributes to the large increase in the inter-laminar fracture toughness of CF/EP composite laminates. The toughening mechanisms activated by the interleaves were also explored based on SEM examinations of the delaminated surfaces.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

Carboxyl multiwalled carbon nanotubes (purity: 95%, diameter: 20–30 nm, length: 10–30 μm , -COOH content: 1.23 wt.%) were supplied by Chengdu Organic Chemistry Co. Ltd., China. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), polysulfone (PSF, $M_w=35000$), N,N-dimethyl acetamide (DMAC), and acetone were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co., Australia. The plain woven CF fabric was provided by Inter-Turbine Advanced Logistics Pty Ltd. The matrix system was Araldite-F (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, Huntsman) and piperidine (Sigma-Aldrich) in weight ratio of 100:5.

2.2. Preparation of PSF nanofibrous membrane and CNTs/polysulfone interleaf

The nanofiber electrospinning unit (NEU) from Kato Tech Co., Ltd, Japan was used to process the polysulfone (PSF) nanofibers. The PSF solution was first prepared by dissolving 5.3 g PSF pellets in pre-determined proportions of N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC)/acetone (9:1w/w) to maintain a 25 wt.% concentration. After stirring for 4 h at 45 °C, the PSF solution was placed in a 20 ml syringe with a stainless steel needle. The PSF nanofibrous membrane was electrospun at a flow rate of 1.5 ml/h and a voltage of 15 kV onto an aluminum foil collector electrode. Then, the PSF nanofiber membrane was used as the “filter paper” to deposit the MWNTs, (which were prepared by dispersing 0.5 wt.% CNTs in distilled water with 1% PVP as surfactant by ultrasonication for 1 h), on both sides by the method of vacuum filtration. The amount of CNTs on the PSF nanofibers membrane was 10 wt.%.

2.3. Preparation of CF/E composite laminates

CF/EP laminates were made of sixteen plies of plain woven CF fabric and Araldite F/piperidine by hand lay-up. A 25 µm thick polyimide film was inserted in the mid-plane of the laminates between the 8th and 9th plies as the initial crack. Simultaneously, the CNTs/PSF nanofibrous paper as interleaf was also placed in the mid-plane. The interleaved composite laminates were then sealed in a vacuum bag, vacuumed for 0.75 h and followed by curing in a hot-press at 120 °C for 16 h under a pressure of 1200 kPa. The carbon fiber in the composite laminates was 60 vol.%; PSF and CNTs in the middle interleaf layer are 17.0 and 1.0 vol.%, respectively. For comparison, composite laminates with the same loading of PSF nanofiber mat (i.e., 17 vol.%) as interleaf and no interleaf were also prepared. Hereafter, we will refer to these 3 types of CF/EP laminates as: CNT/PSF-ICL, PSF-ICL and Control, respectively.

2.4. Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were taken on a Zeiss ULTRA Plus. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was measured by double-cantilever-beams (DCB) on an Instron 5567 machine, based on ASTM D5528. The crack mouth opening displacement rate was 2 mm/min and the initial crack length was 50 mm. At least three samples were tested for each of the 3 types of composite laminates. Dynamic mechanical analysis was performed on a TA Instrument, DMA model 2980 at a fixed frequency 1 Hz and oscillation amplitude 20 µm. The temperature range studied varied from 50 to 180 °C with a heating rate of 3 °C/min. The DMA test samples were made of two plies of plain woven CF fabric interleaved with PSF and CNT/PSF nanofiber mats. Samples with no interleaves were also used as controls.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Morphology of PSF nanofibrous membrane and CNTs/polysulfone interleaf

Fig. 1(a) shows how a CNT/PSF/CNT sandwich composite is prepared. Electrospun polysulfone (PSF) nanofibers, whose diameters range from 150 nm to 500 nm, have a relatively smooth surface, as shown in Fig. 1(b). CNTs were homogeneously dispersed in water with the assistance of PVP, which acted as a surfactant, and remained so after a week (Fig. 1(c)). The PSF nanofiber membrane served as the filter paper, and CNTs were then deposited onto the two surfaces of the membrane, one at a time, by vacuum filtration. Many interconnected pores existed inside the PSF membrane, and water from the CNT solution could easily go through under vacuum filtration, while the CNTs were captured on the nanofiber surfaces. More importantly, these pores promoted epoxy infusion during fabrication of the CR/E laminates. Fig. 1(d) shows an as-prepared sandwich CNT/PSF paper displaying good flexibility. After CNT deposition, the surface of the nanofiber membrane turned from white to completely black, indicating the nanofibrous membrane surfaces were fully covered by CNTs (Fig. 1(e)). Fig. 1(f) shows the cross-section of the CNT/PSF membrane exhibiting two thin CNT layers ~10 µm thick with a PSF nanofiber core ~170 µm thick. CNT distribution on the nanofiber surface is revealed in Fig. 1(g) and it can be seen that the PSF nanofibers are densely decorated with uniformly dispersed CNTs which are several µm in length.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic showing preparation of CNT/PSF sandwich paper; (b) SEM image of electrospun polysulfone (PSF) nanofibers; (c) photo of CNTs-PVP solution in a bottle after a week; (d,e) digital photos of CNTs/PSF sandwich paper; and (f,g) SEM images of cross-section and top surface of CNT/PSF sandwich paper, respectively; large spherical particles in (f) are beads formed on PSF fibre mat.

3.2. Morphology and distribution of polysulfone and CNTs in CF/E laminate

The morphology and distribution of CNTs and PSF microspheres in CF/EP laminates are important to understand the toughening mechanisms. Fig. 2 shows SEM images and EDS spectra of the fracture surfaces of composite laminates with CNT/PSF paper interleave. There are no debonded fibres except CNTs (blue arrows in Fig. 2(b)), PSF microspheres (yellow arrows in Fig. 2) and cavities (red arrows in Fig. 2(a)), indicating that cohesive failure has occurred in the interleaf. EDS spectrum for CNT-rich area in Fig. 2(b) detects no sulfur element implying that CNTs are embedded within the epoxy. Also, EDS spectrum of the microsphere in Fig. 2(c) identifies sulphur, suggesting it is PSF sphere formed by phase separation of PSF nanofiber during curing of epoxy.

Fig. 2. (a) SEM image of fracture surfaces of laminates with CNTs/PSF interleave; and (b,c) EDS spectras of CNTs-rich area and selected microsphere.

From the thermodynamics viewpoint, the distribution of CNTs in the two-phase polymer system can be predicted using the interfacial free energy theory^[28]. There usually exists a selective distribution of fillers in polymer blends due to the different interfacial interactions between filler particles and polymer components^[29]. Fowkes proposed the interfacial energy between two phases, A (EP) and B (PSF), could be described by^[30]:

$$\gamma_{AB} = \gamma_A + \gamma_B - 2(\gamma_A^d \gamma_B^d)^{1/2} - 2(\gamma_A^p \gamma_B^p)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where γ^d and γ^p are the dispersion and polar components of surface energy γ , respectively. The distribution of CNTs in CNT/PSF/EP^[28] can be determined from the wetting coefficient W_a value, which is given by,

$$W_a = \frac{\gamma_{PSF-CNT} - \gamma_{EP-CNT}}{\gamma_{PSF-EP}} \quad (2)$$

where $\gamma_{PSF-CNT}$, γ_{EP-CNT} and γ_{PSF-EP} are interfacial energies between (PSF-CNT), (EP-CNT) and (PSF-EP), respectively. When $w_a > 1$, i.e., $\gamma_{PSF-CNT} > \gamma_{EP-CNT} + \gamma_{PSF-EP}$, CNTs distribute within the EP phase in order to achieve the minimum interfacial free energy of the system; however, CNTs are selectively distributed within the PSF phase when $w_a < -1$; and CNTs are located at the interface between PSF and EP when $-1 < w_a < 1$. The surface energies γ of PSF^[31], EP^[32], and CNT^[33], including the dispersive and polar components, are summarized in Table 1. Hence, based on Eq. (1), $\gamma_{CNT-PSF}$, γ_{PSF-EP} and γ_{CNT-EP} are 4.54, 0.78 and 5.56 mJ/m², respectively. From Eq. (2), w_a is -1.3, indicating that CNTs should be selectively located in the PSF phase. However, Fig. 2 does not support this prediction and explanations in terms of the processing kinetics are given below.

Table 1. Surface energy of EP, PSF and MWNT

Material	γ_s (mJ/m ²)	γ_s^d (mJ/m ²)	γ_s^p (mJ/m ²)
EP	36.3	27.2	9.1
PSF	28.10	18.77	9.34
CNT	45.3	18.4	26.9

In our experiments, the CNTs/PSF interleaf was located in the mid-plane of the laminates, and the epoxy monomer first wetted the thin CNT layer deposited on PSF nanofiber surfaces, and then diffused inwards to the PSF nanofiber mat. Subsequently, the PSF naofibers were gradually dissolved

in epoxy, forming a PSF-EP blend solution, during which interdiffusion between CNT/epoxy and PSF/epoxy would occur due to the relatively low viscosity of the yet uncured epoxy. But as curing continued, PSF began to phase separate from epoxy through the nucleation and growth mechanism, and CNTs were excluded outside the PSF phase. Even though CNTs tended to migrate from epoxy to the PSF phase, the increasing viscosity of both epoxy and PSF during the curing and phase separation process would, to some extent, prevent the CNTs move to the PSF microspheres. Hence, most CNTs remained in the epoxy phase surrounding regions containing the PSF phase as shown in Fig. 2.

3.3 Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of composite

Fig. 3(a) shows mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} , with increasing crack length for the Control, PSF-ICL and CNT/PSF-ICL laminates. G_{IC} is generally independent of crack length for a given laminate. However, G_{IC} can be appreciably increased by the interleaves. Thus, as shown in Fig. 3(b), G_{IC} for the Control is 0.49 kJ/m², PSF-ICL is 0.60 kJ/m² and CNT/PSF-ICL is 0.75 kJ/m², showing increases of 22.5% and 53%, respectively, for the two interleaved laminates compared to the Control laminate.

The failure mechanisms of the controlled and interleaved laminates are mainly governed by their microstructures. Figs. 4(a,b) show SEM images of the fracture surface of the Control laminate. Carbon fibres are cleanly-debonded from epoxy showing poor adhesion with brittle fracture of epoxy between adjacent fibre bundles also displayed. These observations explain the low G_{IC} value of 0.49 kJ/m² obtained.

Typical fracture surface features of PSF-ICL are revealed in Figs. 4(c,d) reflecting the influence of the morphology of this laminate. Different to the Control laminate, the fracture is mainly cohesive through the interleaf showing a highly deformed epoxy matrix (see Fig. 4(c)) containing many exposed PSF microspheres still embedded in epoxy and cavities owing to the debonded and pulled out PSF particles (see Fig. 4(d)). Local matrix plastic deformation can also be seen near the PSF particles (see yellow arrows in Fig. 4(d)). All these failure features give rise to a higher G_{IC} of 0.60 kJ/m².

Fig. 3. (a) Relationship between fracture toughness and crack length of the composite laminates; and (b) average G_{IC} values for Control, PSF-ICL and CNTs/PSF-ICL.

For CNT/PSF-ICL, a considerably rougher fracture surface compared to that of PSF-ICL is shown in Fig. 4(e). The fracture is cohesive (see also Fig. 2) through the interleaf with intense deformation of the epoxy matrix decorated with PSF microspheres and cavities similar to PSF-ICL. In addition, many CNTs are found pulled out from the epoxy matrix, dissipating extra work (see red arrows in Fig. 4(f)). These CNTs along with those much longer CNTs (see yellow arrows in Fig. 4(f)) may have provided some bridging effect, albeit insignificant, to the advancing crack front before being pulled out. Crack

deflection, and hence surface roughness, due to CNTs, which are much smaller than PSF particles, cannot be very efficient. However, the presence of CNTs in the interleaf has further increased the delamination toughness of the CNT/PSF-ICL laminates to G_{IC} of 0.75 kJ/m^2 .

3.4 Dynamic mechanical thermal properties of composite laminates

Fig. 5a displays the temperature dependence of the storage modulus (E') for the Control, PSF-ICL and CNT/PSF-ICL. E' of all laminates first increases slowly with temperature in the initial stage and then exhibits a very sharp drop between 90 and 110 °C, corresponding to the region of the glass transition temperature (T_g). E' of PSF-ICL slightly decreases before the T_g , which might be caused by the reduced crosslinking density of epoxy after the incorporation of PSF. However, a large increase of ~11% for E' is observed around the T_g for CNT/PSF-ICL. This is due to the CNTs in the interleaf which have restricted the mobility of the epoxy chains through strong interfacial interactions.

As for the PSF rich phase, T_g for PSF/CNT-ICL dramatically shifted from 143.2°C to 137.9°C. The approach of these two transition peaks may be caused by the fact that the addition of CNTs could, to some extent, prevent phase separation between epoxy and PSF, and the compatibility between the two phases is therefore improved.

Fig. 5b shows the variation of $\tan \delta$ for the same three composite laminates from 60 to 180 °C. It is clear that there are two transition peaks for PSF-ICL and CNT/PSF-ICL, while only one peak exists for the Control. The appearance of two peaks indicates the occurrence of phase separation during the epoxy curing process. Compared to the Control laminate, the T_g of the epoxy-rich phase for PSF-ICL is decreased from 100.5 to 98.9 °C; but it is increased to 101.8 °C for PSF/CNT-ICL consistent with the stiffening effect of the CNTs. In the PSF-rich phase, the T_g for PSF/CNT-ICL compared to PSF-ICL is significantly reduced from 143.2 to 137.9 °C. This may be caused by the CNTs which have prevented phase separation between epoxy and PSF, thus improving the compatibility of the two phases.

Fig. 4. SEM images of mode I fracture surfaces of composite laminates for (a,b) Control, (c,d) PSF-ICL, and (e,f) CNTs/PSF-ICL.

Fig. 5. (a) Storage modulus (E') and (b) $\tan \delta$ spectra of Control, PSF-ICL and CNTs/PSF-ICL.

4 CONCLUSION

In this work, CNT/PSF sandwich paper was prepared by depositing CNTs on both sides of PSF nanofiber mat by vacuum filtration. The as-prepared paper had good flexibility and its surfaces were fully covered by CNTs. The CNT/PSF paper was used as interleafs to study the delamination toughening effect on CF/EP composite laminates. DCB test showed the mode I toughness (G_{IC}) for

CNT/PSF interleaved laminates was increased by 53% compared to the controls due to intense deformation of the epoxy matrix promoted by the PSF microparticles and pull-out of the CNTs. The insert of CNT/PSF interleaves in CF/EP laminates improved the storage modulus caused by the CNTs. DMA results also confirmed that better compatibility between epoxy and PSF could be achieved by adding CNTs.

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